

Dual infection of plants with ragged stunt and other virus diseases

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In the Philippines, there are five virus and virus-like diseases of rice plants – grassy stunt, orange leaf, ragged stunt, tungro, and yellow dwarf (orange leaf and yellow dwarf are of minor importance). Rice plants can be infected with both tungro and grassy stunt. Therefore, dual infection of ragged stunt and grassy stunt or ragged stunt and tungro was studied by inoculating seedlings of TN1 with the respective viruliferous insects in the greenhouse.

Rice plants were infected with both grassy stunt and ragged stunt (Fig. 1, 2). The dually infected plants had the symptoms of both grassy stunt (profuse tillering and narrow leaf blades) and ragged stunt (ragged leaves). They were much more stunted, particularly at later growth stages. The tips of some leaves were twisted.

Rice plants were also infected with both tungro and ragged stunt (Fig. 3). The infected plants showed stunting, yellowing of leaves (a tungro symptom), and ragged leaves (ragged stunt symptom).

1. A rice plant infected with both ragged stunt and grassy stunt.

2. Close-up of the dually infected plant, showing ragged leaves.

3. A rice plant infected with both ragged stunt and tungro.

The dual infection indicates absence of cross protection either between ragged stunt and grassy stunt or between ragged stunt and tungro. Hence, the causal agent of ragged stunt is not closely related to the causal agent of grassy stunt or of tungro. ❧

A study of vein-swellings of rice plants infected with ragged stunt

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One symptom of rice ragged stunt disease is the appearance of narrow, elongated swellings of veins, a result of proliferation of phloem cells in vascular bundles.

Vein-swelling seems to be a more appropriate term than *gall* to describe that symptom. Galls have been defined as large swellings on plant tissues caused by the invasion of parasites such as fungi and bacteria, or as excrescences of plants caused by fungi, mites, or insects. The definitions imply that the causal agent or parasite is localized in or restricted to the galls. That does not hold true for malformations due to the systemic

infection of a virus, because the virus also spreads to other plant parts. Therefore, it has been suggested that virus-induced abnormalities be classified as enations or tumors rather than as galls. For ragged stunt disease, vein-swelling is preferred because it is both specific and descriptive.

When 60 rice varieties and lines that had been naturally infected with ragged stunt were examined at or after the late tillering stage, all had vein-swellings. Of the 170 diseased hills examined, 96% had vein-swellings. Not every diseased hill of some rices had vein-swellings. For instance, only about 50% of diseased hills of Raminad strain 3 had them. Nor did every tiller in a diseased hill have vein-swellings. Of the 794 tillers of diseased plants of 18 rices examined, 66% had

them. The percentage of tillers with vein-swellings seemed to increase as the plants grew older.

The vein-swellings appeared on leaf sheaths, blades, and culms at varying frequencies. Of the 1,006 vein swellings examined, 72% appeared on the leaf sheath, 21% on the blades, and 7% on the culms. The vein-swellings were not distributed evenly on the leaf sheaths, nor on the blades. About 90% of those on the leaf sheaths appeared on the upper half. About 60% of those on the leaf blades were on the lower half, most near the collar.

The vein-swellings were on the outer surfaces of leaf sheaths or on the lower surfaces of blades. None were observed on the opposite sides, possibly because of the location of phloem cells in the tissue